

ANTIMICROBIAL PROPERTIES OF IONOGENIC INULIN DERIVATIVES

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Relevance: World medical practice faces the problem of increasing number of infectious diseases that are difficult to treat with known antimicrobial agents. First of all, this is due to a sharp increase in the number of resistant microorganisms to existing drugs and a decrease in their therapeutic effectiveness due to uncontrolled administration. In such conditions, the need for the development of new antimicrobial agents based on natural polymers increases. Of particular interest are compounds that can combine antimicrobial activity with a minimal risk of side effects. It is known that polysaccharides such as chitosan, pectin, alginic acid and their derivatives have a wide spectrum of antimicrobial action. At the same time, antimicrobial polysaccharides do not exhibit toxic effects and do not accumulate in the body. Based on this, research aimed at obtaining new polysaccharide derivatives with antimicrobial action remains relevant.

Purpose of the study: Synthesis and study of antimicrobial activity of new inulin derivatives containing ionogenic anionic groups.

Materials and methods: To synthesize ionogenic derivatives of inulin, the polysaccharide was preliminarily functionalized with thionyl chloride in a dimethylformamide medium for 3 hours and $t_o=70^{\circ}\text{C}$. Then, a molecule of sulfamic acid was added to the synthesized chlorinulin. The reaction took place in an aqueous medium, at $t_o=50^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 3 hours. The resulting sample was dissolved in water and purified by dialysis for 48 hours and separated by sublimation drying. The degree of substitution of the synthesized sample was 25 mol%, the $\text{pK}\alpha$ value was 4.3, and the zeta potential value was -8 mV.

The antimicrobial properties of the synthesized inulin derivative were evaluated by diffusion in agar at a concentration of 1-5 mg/ml. *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were selected as microbial cultures.

Results: Microbiological studies in vitro have shown that the synthesized inulin derivative has antimicrobial properties against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The zone of microorganism growth inhibition depends on the concentration of the studied sample. This indicates a pronounced dose-dependent activity of the compounds. With increasing concentration, the zone of microorganism growth inhibition increases. The most effective antimicrobial properties are observed at a concentration of 5 mg/ml, where the growth inhibition zone for *Staphylococcus aureus* is 15 ± 1.2 mm, and in the case of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* this value reaches 21 ± 1.5 mm. The obtained results indicate the prospects of using inulin derivatives as a basis for creating new polymeric antimicrobial agents for local or internal use.

Conclusions: Thus, as a result of the conducted research, we synthesized inulin derivatives containing acidic ionogenic groups in the structure. Microbiological studies in vitro have proven that the introduction of anionic groups into polymer molecules imparts antimicrobial properties to inulin, the level of which depends on the concentration.